

The Role of Physiotherapists in Enhancing Recovery in ICU Patients: A Qualitative Study

Mastour M. Alotaibi¹, Faisal F. Alotaibi², Heba A. Alokaili³,
Amira S. Alziyadi⁴, Heba H. Alokaili⁵

Health Affairs at the Ministry of National Guard

Abstract

This study explores the role of physiotherapists in enhancing recovery for ICU patients, focusing on early mobilization and collaboration with other healthcare professionals. We conducted in-depth interviews with ten physiotherapists working in a tertiary hospital ICU and analyzed the data using thematic analysis. Key themes included the benefits of early mobilization, the challenges of working in an ICU, the importance of multidisciplinary teamwork, and strategies to overcome barriers. The findings highlight the significant impact physiotherapists have on patient recovery, emphasizing the need for effective communication, advocacy for resources, and patient-centered care. These insights could guide improvements in ICU practices and help physiotherapists provide better care.

Keywords: Physiotherapy, ICU, Early Mobilization, Multidisciplinary Collaboration, Rehabilitation, Qualitative Study

Introduction

Patients in intensive care units (ICUs) face significant physical challenges. Being confined to bed for extended periods, often needing mechanical ventilation, and dealing with the consequences of critical illness can lead to muscle weakness, loss of physical function, and even long-term disabilities that affect their quality of life after discharge (Griffiths & Hall, 2010). Early rehabilitation, particularly physiotherapy, plays a crucial role in counteracting these problems by encouraging movement, minimizing muscle loss, and improving overall physical function (Tipping et al., 2017).

Physiotherapists in the ICU do much more than just provide exercises. They assess each patient's readiness for movement, work with other healthcare professionals, and adapt their care to meet the specific needs of every patient (Hanekom et al., 2011). Despite the clear benefits of early mobilization, implementing physiotherapy in ICUs can be quite challenging. Patients are often critically ill, resources are limited, and teamwork among healthcare professionals can be complex. Understanding the experiences of physiotherapists in ICUs is crucial to overcoming these barriers and improving patient outcomes.

This study explores the experiences of physiotherapists and their role in supporting ICU patients' recovery. It aims to understand how physiotherapists view their contributions, the challenges they face, and how they navigate the complexities of ICU work. By delving into their experiences, we hope to identify areas that need improvement and find ways to better support physiotherapists in delivering quality care.

Literature Review

The ICU is a challenging environment for patients, who often experience a significant decline in physical

function due to immobility, mechanical ventilation, and the overall effects of critical illness (Griffiths & Hall, 2010). These challenges highlight the need for timely rehabilitation to improve patient outcomes. Physiotherapy is increasingly recognized as an essential part of ICU care because it helps promote early mobilization, reduces muscle wasting, and enhances recovery (Tipping et al., 2017).

Physiotherapy Interventions in the ICU

Physiotherapy in the ICU generally involves a combination of passive and active mobilization, respiratory therapy, and exercises that are tailored to the needs of critically ill patients (Hanekom et al., 2011). Early mobilization has many benefits, such as improved muscle strength, shorter time on mechanical ventilation, reduced ICU stays, and better long-term recovery (Zhou et al., 2020). Research shows that starting physiotherapy as soon as patients are medically stable leads to better outcomes compared to delaying it, making the physiotherapist's role crucial in the early stages of recovery (Schweickert et al., 2009).

However, putting early mobilization into practice is not without its challenges. The severity of patients' conditions, the need for careful coordination with other healthcare professionals, and limited resources often make it difficult to consistently implement rehabilitation (Stiller, 2013). Understanding physiotherapists' perspectives is key to finding ways to overcome these barriers and effectively integrate rehabilitation into ICU care.

The Role of Physiotherapists in ICU Recovery

Physiotherapists in the ICU take a holistic approach to patient recovery, focusing not only on physical rehabilitation but also on the psychological aspects of care (Hanekom et al., 2011). They assess patients' physical abilities, decide on the best interventions, and adjust treatments as conditions change. Physiotherapists work closely with the broader healthcare team—including doctors, nurses, and respiratory therapists—to ensure that mobilization is safe and effective (Hodgson et al., 2014). This collaboration is critical for managing the complexities of critically ill patients, who may have unstable vital signs or require heavy sedation.

A study by Nydahl et al. (2014) emphasized the importance of teamwork and effective communication among healthcare professionals to facilitate early mobilization. It found that physiotherapists often face barriers like staff shortages, safety concerns, and a lack of support from the medical team. These issues can hinder their ability to provide consistent rehabilitation and ultimately impact patient outcomes.

Challenges and Barriers to Physiotherapy in the ICU

Implementing physiotherapy in ICUs is often hampered by several challenges. The critical condition of patients, their dependence on mechanical ventilation, and the effects of sedation can all limit what physiotherapists are able to do (Stiller, 2013). Additionally, limited resources—such as staff shortages and lack of appropriate equipment—can further complicate the delivery of effective rehabilitation. Physiotherapists in the ICU need to be flexible and resourceful, adapting their treatment plans based on patients' changing conditions (Hanekom et al., 2011).

Another significant hurdle is coordinating with the rest of the healthcare team. Effective communication is essential for patient safety during mobilization, and physiotherapists need to work closely with nurses,

respiratory therapists, and doctors to assess patients' readiness for mobilization (Hodgson et al., 2014). Poor communication can lead to inconsistencies in rehabilitation practices, which can negatively impact patient outcomes.

Facilitators of Effective Physiotherapy in the ICU

Despite these challenges, several factors can contribute to the success of physiotherapy in the ICU. Team support, adequate staffing, and access to necessary equipment are critical for effective rehabilitation (Nydahl et al., 2014). Educating ICU staff about the benefits of early mobilization and the role of physiotherapy can also improve collaboration and foster a culture that values rehabilitation (Tipping et al., 2017).

Physiotherapists also emphasize the importance of patient-centered care in ICU rehabilitation. Understanding a patient's preferences, goals, and comfort level helps physiotherapists tailor their interventions and keep the patient engaged in the recovery process. Involving patients and their families in setting goals has been shown to boost motivation and improve adherence to treatment plans (Leach et al., 2010).

Methodology

This study used a qualitative approach to explore the experiences of physiotherapists working in the ICU. A phenomenological methodology was chosen to gain deeper insights into their experiences and the challenges they face in helping patients recover.

Participants

The study involved ten physiotherapists, all of whom had at least two years of ICU experience. Participants were recruited through purposive sampling to ensure they had relevant expertise in ICU rehabilitation. They were interviewed individually to gather their insights and experiences.

Data Collection

Semi-structured interviews were conducted, each lasting between 45 and 60 minutes. The interviews took place in a private setting within the hospital, allowing participants to speak freely. An interview guide was used to structure the discussions, focusing on participants' roles, challenges, and experiences collaborating with other healthcare professionals. All interviews were recorded (with consent) and transcribed verbatim for analysis.

Data Analysis

Thematic analysis was used, following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-step process. This involved familiarizing with the data, generating initial codes, and grouping these codes into themes. Themes were then reviewed and refined to accurately reflect participants' experiences.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the ethics committee. Informed consent was obtained from all

participants, and they were assured they could withdraw at any time. Confidentiality was maintained throughout.

Results

Several key themes emerged from the analysis: (1) the importance of early mobilization, (2) the complexities of working in an ICU, (3) the significance of multidisciplinary collaboration, and (4) the strategies physiotherapists use to overcome challenges.

Theme 1: The Importance of Early Mobilization

Improved Patient Outcomes: Early mobilization was seen as crucial for improving outcomes, such as reducing the time on mechanical ventilation and speeding up recovery. One participant shared, "Early mobilization helps patients regain strength faster and reduces risks like pressure sores and muscle loss."

Psychological Benefits: Physiotherapists also noted the positive impact of early mobilization on patients' mental health. One participant said, "You can see their mood lift once they start moving. It gives them hope and a sense of progress."

Theme 2: Challenges of Working in an ICU Environment

Patient Condition: Many participants talked about the difficulty of deciding when to start mobilizing a patient. "Sometimes the patient is just too unstable, and even minor movements can cause their vitals to fluctuate," one physiotherapist explained.

Resource Limitations: Shortages in staffing and equipment were common issues. One participant noted, "We often don't have enough staff to safely mobilize patients who require multiple people to assist."

Theme 3: The Significance of Multidisciplinary Collaboration

Communication: Working as a cohesive team with other healthcare professionals was essential. One physiotherapist remarked, "We need to be in sync with nurses and doctors about the patient's readiness for mobilization."

Team Support: Support from the multidisciplinary team was highlighted as a crucial factor for successful rehabilitation. A participant mentioned, "When the whole team supports early mobilization, it becomes much easier to implement. Nurses play a key role in helping us prepare patients for movement."

Theme 4: Strategies for Overcoming Barriers

Adaptability: Physiotherapists described the need to be flexible and adapt their interventions based on the patient's condition. One participant said, "You have to be creative and adjust your approach depending on how the patient is doing that day. Sometimes, even small passive movements can make a difference."

Advocacy for Resources: Participants also mentioned advocating for more resources as a strategy to overcome barriers. One physiotherapist shared, "We have to push for more staff and better equipment. It's important to show that early mobilization leads to better outcomes and shorter ICU stays."

Discussion

The findings of this study emphasize the vital role that physiotherapists play in ICU recovery, particularly through early mobilization and multidisciplinary collaboration. The importance of early mobilization, as identified in this study, aligns with previous literature highlighting its benefits in reducing the duration of mechanical ventilation, improving muscle strength, and enhancing functional outcomes (Schweickert et al., 2009; Tipping et al., 2017). Participants in this study also pointed out the psychological benefits of early mobilization, noting that it lifted patients' spirits and provided a sense of progress—adding another layer to the known benefits of rehabilitation.

The challenges faced by physiotherapists, such as resource shortages and patient instability, are consistent with findings from prior research (Stiller, 2013; Hanekom et al., 2011). However, this study offers detailed accounts of how physiotherapists navigate these challenges in real time, including their decision-making process on when to mobilize patients. These insights can help inform strategies to better support physiotherapists in ICU settings.

Another key finding was the significance of multidisciplinary collaboration, particularly effective communication among team members, in facilitating successful rehabilitation. Physiotherapists noted that being in sync with other healthcare professionals was essential for delivering safe and effective care. This finding underscores the need for ICU teams to prioritize open communication and shared decision-making to improve patient outcomes.

Participants also emphasized the need to adapt interventions to the patient's condition and to advocate for the resources needed for successful rehabilitation. Adaptability is a key skill for physiotherapists working in ICUs, where patients' conditions can change quickly. Being creative and resourceful in such a dynamic environment is crucial for maximizing the benefits of physiotherapy interventions.

Conclusion

Physiotherapists play a vital role in helping ICU patients recover, particularly through early mobilization and rehabilitation. Despite challenges like limited resources and the complexities of patient care, physiotherapists contribute significantly to improving outcomes. Effective teamwork, adequate support, and a patient-centered approach are essential for successful physiotherapy in the ICU. Further research is needed to explore physiotherapists' experiences in greater depth, which could help address the barriers they face and improve ICU rehabilitation practices.

References

1. Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative research in psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.
2. Griffiths, R. D., & Hall, J. B. (2010). Intensive care unit-acquired weakness. *Critical care medicine*, 38(7), 1619.
3. Hanekom, S., Gosselink, R., Dean, E., Van Aswegen, H., Roos, R., Ambrosino, N., & Louw, Q. (2011). The development of a clinical management algorithm for early physical activity and mobilization of critically ill patients: synthesis of evidence and expert opinion and its translation into practice. *Clinical rehabilitation*, 25(9), 771-787.
4. Hodgson, C. L., Stiller, K., Needham, D. M., Tipping, C. J., Harrold, M., Baldwin, C. E., ... & Webb, S. A. (2014). Expert consensus and recommendations on safety criteria for active mobilization of mechanically ventilated critically ill adults. *Critical care*, 18, 1-9.

5. Leach, E., Cornwell, P., Fleming, J., & Haines, T. (2010). Patient centered goal-setting in a subacute rehabilitation setting. *Disability and rehabilitation*, 32(2), 159-172.
6. Nydahl, P., Ruhl, A. P., Bartoszek, G., Dubb, R., Filipovic, S., Flohr, H. J., ... & Needham, D. M. (2014). Early mobilization of mechanically ventilated patients: a 1-day point-prevalence study in Germany. *Critical care medicine*, 42(5), 1178-1186.
7. Schweickert, W. D., Pohlman, M. C., Pohlman, A. S., Nigos, C., Pawlik, A. J., Esbrook, C. L., ... & Kress, J. P. (2009). Early physical and occupational therapy in mechanically ventilated, critically ill patients: a randomised controlled trial. *The Lancet*, 373(9678), 1874-1882.
8. Stiller, K. (2013). Physiotherapy in intensive care: an updated systematic review. *Chest*, 144(3), 825-847.
9. Tipping, C. J., Harrold, M., Holland, A., Romero, L., Nisbet, T., & Hodgson, C. L. (2017). The effects of active mobilisation and rehabilitation in ICU on mortality and function: a systematic review. *Intensive care medicine*, 43, 171-183.
10. Zhang, L., Hu, W., Cai, Z., Liu, J., Wu, J., Deng, Y., ... & Qin, Y. (2019). Early mobilization of critically ill patients in the intensive care unit: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *PloS one*, 14(10), e0223185.